

Scores Obtained by Criterion and Category: Criteria of relevance and appropriateness

Primary studies	Paper	Criterion													TOTAL
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	
P1	Psychological Safety, Leadership and Non-Technical Debt in LargeScale Agile Software Development	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P2	"The Second Vice is Lying, the First is Running into Debt." Antecedents and Mitigating Practices of Social Debt: An Exploratory Study in Distributed Software Development Teams"	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	12
P3	A Multivocal Literature Review on Non-Technical Debt in Software Development: An Insight into Process, Social, People, Organizational, and Culture Debt	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	11,5
P4	Software architecture social debt: Managing the incommunicability factor	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	11
P5	Splicing Community and Software Architecture Smells in Agile Teams: An industrial Study	1	1	0,5	1	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	11,5
P6	Exploring Community Smells in Open-Source: An Automated Approach	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	11,5
P7	Understanding community smells variability: A statistical approach	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	12
P8	The architect's role in community shepherding	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12,5
P9	An Empirical Study of Social Debt in Open-Source Projects: Social Drivers and the "Known Devil" Community Smell	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	12
P10	Debt Stories: Capturing Social and Technical Debt in the Industry	1	1	1	1	1	0	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	11,5
P11	Gender Diversity and Community Smells: A Double-Replication Study on Brazilian Software Teams	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	12,5
P12	Effective Social Productivity Measurements During Software Development: An Empirical Study	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	0,5	11,5
P13	Gender diversity and women in software teams: How do they affect community smells?	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0	1	1	11
P14	Analyzing the Relationship between Community and Design Smells in Open-Source Software Projects: An Empirical Study	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	12
P15	Locating community smells in software development processes using higher-order network centralities	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	0,5	1	0,5	0,5	1	10
P16	Discovering community patterns in open-source: a systematic approach and its evaluation	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	11,5
P17	Measuring affective states from technical debt: A psychoempirical software engineering experiment	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	11,5
P18	Community smell occurrence prediction on multi-granularity by developer-oriented features and process metrics	0,5	0	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	0	1	1	9,5
P19	The influence of Technical Debt on software developer morale	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	0	0,5	1	10
P20	Towards Understanding the Social and Organizational Dimensions of Software Architecting	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	11,5
P21	Are we working well with others? How the multi team systems impact software quality	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12,5
P22	Towards Power Relationship Dynamics and Community Smells in the Proprietary Software Ecosystem	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P23	In Search of Socio-Technical Congruence: A Large-Scale Longitudinal Study	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P24	Good Fences Make Good Neighbours? on the Impact of Cultural and Geographical Dispersion on Community Smells	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P25	The emotional side of software developers in JIRA	0,5	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	11,5
P26	Preliminary Insights on Industry Practices for Addressing Fairness Debt	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12,5
P27	Community smells-The sources of social debt: A systematic literature review	0,5	1	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	11
P28	Predicting the emergence of community smells using socio-technical metrics: A machine-learning approach	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
P29	Impacts of software community patterns on process and product: An empirical study	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
P30	Improving the detection of community smells through socio-technical and sentiment analysis	1	0,5	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P31	Learning to Detect Community Smells in Open Source Software Projects	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P32	Refactoring Community Smells: An Empirical Study on the Software Practitioners of Bangladesh	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	12,5

P33	Refactoring Community Smells in the Wild: The Practitioner's Field Manual	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P34	On the Detection of Community Smells Using Genetic Programming-based Ensemble Classifier Chain	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	0,5	0,5	11
P35	Splicing Community Patterns and Smells: A Preliminary Study	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	11,5
P36	Predicting Community Smells' Occurrence on Individual Developers by Sentiments	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	11
P37	An empirical study on the effect of community smells on bug prediction	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	12
P38	Understanding the Relationship between Missing Link Community Smell and Fix-inducing Changes	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	0,5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12
P39	Navigating social debt and its link with technical debt in large-scale agile software development projects	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
P40	Revealing social debt with the CAFFEA framework: An antidote to architectural debt	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
P41	Gender Diversity and Community Smells: Insights from the Trenches.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	12
P42	Beyond technical aspects: How do community smells influence the intensity of code smells?	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
P43	The Pandora's box of social, process, and people debts in software engineering	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
P44	What is social debt in software engineering	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
P45	Social debt in software engineering: insights from industry.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
Criterion Total		0,8	0,91111	0,96667	0,9889	0,988889	0,9111	0,73333	0,94444	0,988889	0,977778	0,744444	0,93333	0,97778	11,86667

Category	Score
Clarity	0,856
Rigor	0,932
Relevancia	0,861
Credibility	0,956